

Antyodaya: From Ancient Wisdom to Practical Implementation

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ABSTRACT

Antyodaya is a socio-economic philosophy that aims to extend the benefits of development to the very bottom of society. This concept is based on the fundamental principles of "Integral Humanism" propounded by Pandit Deendayal Upadhyaya. However, the base of this thought was, already propounded in ancient scriptures, including the Vedas, Upanishads and the Bhagavad Gita, which advocate for the welfare of all beings and the duty of the state to protect the vulnerable. The various Antyodaya Yojanas aims to provide assistance to families living in extreme poverty. The fundamental principle of the 'Integral Human Philosophy' propounded by Pandit Deendayal Upadhyaya is 'Antyodaya,' which means the rise or upliftment of the person at the bottom of society. This principle presents an inclusive development model based on thought of Bharat. Against this ideological backdrop, the Government of India implemented the 'Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY),' which aims to ensure food security by providing subsidized food grains to the poorest of poor families in the country. This developmental model of Deendayal is useful not only for Bharat but for the entire world. Today, the 17 Sustainable Development Goals formulated by countries around the world also reflect the concern for the protection of humanity. First two goals 'No Poverty' can be achieved to some extent and 'Zero Hunger'

can be totally achieved through 'Antyodaya Anna Yojana' (AAY). The primary objective of this paper is to provide a thorough analysis of the philosophical and conceptual dimensions of Upadhyay's 'Antyodaya' and to evaluate its practical implementation and effectiveness through the 'Antyodaya Anna Yojana'.

Introduction

The concept of Antyodaya, articulated by Pandit Deendayal Upadhyaya, is a comprehensive philosophy that integrates several foundational Indian and global ideas. It embodies Swami Vivekananda's ideal of "Nar Seva Narayan Seva," Jain Acharya Samant Bhadra's concept of "Sarvodaya Teerth," John Ruskin's idea of Antyodaya, Mahatma Gandhi's principle of Sarvodaya, and Socrates' notion of Satya Sadhana. Pandit Deendayal Upadhyaya stood firmly against exploitative forces, social evils, and ostentatious living, and envisioned a society based on harmony and balance. The philosophical foundation of Antyodaya is Advaita (non-dualism), while its practical approach emphasizes coordination between nature and society. The essence of Antyodaya is deeply embedded in almost all Indian scriptures.¹

The Shrimad Bhagavad Geeta (श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता) expresses this spirit in one of its verses:

सर्वभूतस्थमात्मानं सर्वभूतानि चात्मनि।

ईक्षते योगयुक्तात्मा सर्वत्र समदर्शनः॥² 6/23 Geeta

Meaning of the above is that if a person established in yoga perceives the same Self in all beings, experiences oneself in everyone and everyone within oneself and therefore maintains an equal vision everywhere. Thus, this verse makes it clear that Antyodaya is not merely a social or economic program, but a duty rooted in a profound spiritual truth, grounded in 'Samadarsana' (equal vision) and integral oneness. When a yogi perceives the Self in all beings and all beings within the Self, the 'last person' in society is no longer seen as separate or inferior. This vision dissolves discrimination and gives rise to compassion, which naturally expresses itself through 'Nişkama karma' (selfless action). Consequently, Antyodaya ceases to be an act of charity or welfare and becomes a moral and spiritual obligation, where the upliftment of the weakest is experienced as one's own upliftment.

Similarly, the ideas of 'आत्मवत् सर्वभूतेषु' and 'सर्वभूता हितो रतः' reflect the spirit of oneness and Antyodaya by emphasizing empathy and the welfare of all beings. The Bhagavad Gita also implicitly

upholds this philosophy through its emphasis on unity, compassion, and universal well-being. Upadhyaya's concern extended to society as a whole. He firmly believed that true national progress is possible only when the person at the lowest rung of society rises, and that the advancement of both society and the nation is fundamentally rooted in the principle of Antyodaya.³

Deendayal Upadhyaya's vision of Antyodaya was rooted in national interest and the dignity of national labor. He regarded national labor as a fundamental duty of every citizen. His conception of Antyodaya emphasized that while social welfare programs should be inclusive, priority must always be accorded to the person at the lowest level of society. He advocated for villages to remain the central focus of governmental initiatives and stressed the importance of maintaining a balanced relationship between rural and urban development. Consequently, this philosophy holds even greater relevance in the contemporary context, as reflected in the implementation of various Antyodaya-oriented programs today.⁴

Pandit Deendayal Upadhyaya possessed a deep understanding of the ground realities of the country, which made his ideas highly relevant at the grassroots level. From the very beginning, the adoption of foreign policies in Bharat fostered a sense of selfishness within society, gradually shifting the collective outlook from "we" to "I." As a result, the nation became divided into two stark economic classes, the extremely poor and the extremely rich. A significant section of India's population continues to struggle to meet even their basic needs. Upadhyaya believed that this economically disadvantaged section must be freed from constant financial anxiety. He emphasized that families living below the poverty line, barely able to sustain themselves, should be uplifted and brought above the poverty threshold. To achieve this, he proposed the concept of Antyodaya. He envisioned a society in which every individual has access to work and the freedom to choose employment according to their abilities and interests. At the same time, he stressed that the economically prosperous sections of society bear a moral responsibility to support poorer families and help them attain a life of dignity and self-respect.⁵

Efforts toward Antyodaya in Contemporary India

In present-day India, numerous welfare schemes are being implemented in accordance with the philosophy of Antyodaya, with the objective of promoting social justice and prosperity, inspired by the ideal of Ram Rajya. These initiatives seek to translate the vision of a just and equitable society into reality. Some notable examples include, Jan Dhan Yojana, Ayushman Bharat, Ujjwala Yojana, Antyodaya Anna Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana etc. The ultimate goal of these schemes is to uplift the last person in society, empower them to lead a dignified life, and enable them to become self-reliant and capable participants in the nation's development.⁶

Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY):

At present, this scheme provides food grains to the poorest among the poor at highly subsidized rates, ₹2–3 per kilogram for wheat and rice, thereby ensuring food security. Eligible families are provided 35 kilograms of food grains per month free of cost. The Antyodaya Anna Yojana was launched in the year 2000 by Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee with the objective of protecting extremely poor households from hunger and starvation. Subsequently, the National Food Security Act, 2013 was enacted, further strengthening the framework of food security in the country.⁷

Starting of AAY:

In an interview regarding the launch of the **Antyodaya Anna Yojana**, the then **Union Minister for Food and Civil Supplies, Shri Shanta Kumar**, recalled that upon assuming office he discovered a disturbing reality: nearly five crore people in the country went to bed hungry, while government warehouses were overflowing with food grains, much of which was deteriorating due to lack of storage. The then Chief Minister of Punjab, Shri Parkash Singh Badal, also pointed out that the stockpiles were so excessive that there was scarcely any space left to store additional grain. This stark contradiction deeply troubled him. When, Shri Shanta Kumar presented the proposal for the Antyodaya Anna Yojana to the Union Cabinet, approval was delayed for five to six months due to financial concerns. Shortly thereafter, he read a newspaper report about 15 deaths due to starvation in Kalahandi, Maharashtra, which prompted him to immediately meet Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee. He conveyed that despite overflowing granaries, people were dying of hunger and remarked that under such circumstances, they both stood morally culpable. This deeply moved Atal Ji. Shri Shanta Kumar then requested that the food security scheme be launched on 25 December, Atal Ji's birthday. Atal Bihari Vajpayee agreed and instructed the Finance-Minister to initiate the scheme immediately. As a result, the Antyodaya Anna Yojana was launched without awaiting formal cabinet approval, marking a decisive step toward ensuring food security for the poorest sections of society.⁸

In 2003–04, out of the total identified Below Poverty Line (BPL) households in India, only the poorest 23 percent were selected as beneficiaries under the Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY). In the present scenario, this coverage has expanded, and approximately 38 percent of BPL families are now included as beneficiaries of the scheme. The Government of India has issued specific guidelines for the selection of families under the Antyodaya Anna Yojana. Generally, priority is given to BPL households with an annual income of less than ₹15,000, households with elderly members above 60 years of age, and

families headed by or including widows and persons with disabilities. Selected households are provided subsidized food grains to ensure their basic food requirements. In addition to supporting extremely poor households, the government has strengthened food security by providing nutritional support to children registered at Anganwadi centers and by implementing the Mid-Day Meal Scheme in schools. Together, these measures aim to ensure comprehensive food security for the most vulnerable sections of society.⁹

Administrative implementation of AAY in Himachal Pradesh:

At present, in Himachal Pradesh, APL, APLT, BPL, AAY, and PHH cards are primarily in circulation for the distribution of ration and certain other facilities. The details of these cards and the associated population in Himachal Pradesh can be understood on the basis of the following tables.

Table No 01. Number of Ration Cards (Year-wise) in Himachal Pradesh

S N	Year	1.Total APL cards (Beyond NFSA)	2.Inco -me Tax payee APL 'APL T'	COVERED UNDER NFSA				7.TOTA L (7=1+2+ 6)	8. Ann a- pur na Car ds	9. Tibe tan Car ds	10.TOT AL OF ALL CARDS (10= 7+8+9)	% of AAY Card s to NFS A	% of NFS A Cards to total cards	% of AAY Card s to total Card s
				3.Total BPL Cards	4.Total AAY Cards	5.PHH Cards	6. TOTA L (6=3+4 +5)							
1	2015 -16	1129835	NA	298502	194874	203194	696570	1826505	1700	3928	1832133	27.98	38.02	10.64
2	2016 -17	1120410	NA	294822	194061	219483	708466	1828878	1020	3858	1833756	27.39	38.63	10.58
3	2017 -18	1126884	NA	293740	193499	223134	710373	1837257	1014	4411	1842682	27.24	38.54	10.50
4	2018 -19	1155178	NA	280618	185070	221238	686926	1842104	668	4263	1847035	26.94	37.20	10.02
5	2019 -20	1208968	NA	279308	178522	219816	677646	1884614	29	NA	1886643	26.34	35.91	9.46
6	2020 -21	1174966	67607	273678	171202	225921	670801	1915374	33	NA	1913408	25.52	35.06	8.95
7	2021 -22	1127767	77324	276506	169733	296725	742964	1948055	33	NA	1948088	22.85	38.14	8.71

8	2022 -23	1146840	73675	280673	168179	305409	754261	1973776	14	NA	1974790	22.30	38.20	8.52
9	2023 -24	1137019	67435	283086	165690	305254	754030	1958484	07	NA	1958491	21.97	38.49	8.46
10	July, 2025	1137454	60927	279649	161518	304456	745623	1948004	00	NA	1944004	21.66	38.35	8.31
Average		1149532	34697	284058	178235	252463	714766	1896305	451. 8	4115	1898103	26.44	37.65	9.615
SD		26736.6 5	33160 .72	7602.8 7	12766. 33	43935. 78	32188. 27	59218.9 9	611. 63	264. 91	56441.3 1	4.29	1.23	0.803
CV		2.33%	95.61	2.68	0.0716	0.1740	4.5	3.12	135. 4	-100	2.97	16.21	3.26	8.35
CAGR		0.80%	UD	-0.96	-2.064	4.595	1.00	1.00	-100	3.00	1.00	-3.00	0.00	-2.31
Maximum		1208968	77324	298502	194874	305409	754261	1973776	1020	4411	1974790	33.67	38.63	10.64
Minimum		1120410	60927	273678	161518	203194	670801	1826505	00	3858	183213	21.66	35.06	8.31

Major Findings from Table-1

1. The average number of APL cards from 2015 to 2025 (data for 2024–25 not included) was 1,149,532. The number of APL cards increased at a CAGR of 0.80% per year during this period. The maximum number of APL cards was recorded in 2019–20, while the minimum was in 2016–17.
2. The average number of NFSA cards from 2015 to 2025 (data for 2024–25 not included) was 714,766. Ration cards under NFSA increased at a CAGR of 1% per year during this period. The maximum number of beneficiary families was observed in 2022–23, while the minimum was in 2020–21.
3. The average number of AAY cards from 2015 to 2025 (data for 2024–25 not included) was 178,235. During this period, ration cards under BPL declined at a CAGR of –0.96%, and AAY cards decreased at a CAGR of –2.064% per year, whereas ration cards under PHH increased at a CAGR of 4.595%. Over these ten years, the maximum number of beneficiary families was recorded in 2015–16, and the minimum in the current year (2025–26). From April 2015 to July 2025, the percentage of AAY cards to total NFSA cards declined significantly from 27.98% to 21.66%, showing a consistent year-wise reduction. Similarly, the percentage of AAY cards with respect to the total number of ration cards declined from 10.64% to 8.31%, with a decrease observed in every year.

Table 2. Population Associated (Year-wise) with the Ration Cards

S r o	Sessi on	1.Total Membe rs having APL cards (Beyon d NFSA)	1A. Incom e tax payer APL Mem	POPULATION COVERED UNDER NFSA				% of mem in AAY To NFS A	6. TOTAL (6=1+5)	7. Total Mem Unde r Ann a- purn a	8. Total Mem of Tibbe t	9.Total Of All Mem (9=6+7 +8)	% of Mem . Unde r AAY To total Mem
				2. Total Mem Having BPL- Cards	3. Total Mem under AAY Cards	4. Total Mems Having PHH Cards	5. All Mems Under NFSA (5=2+3 +4)						
1	2015 -16	4622104	NA	1336880	930262	838913	3106055	29.94	7728159	1700	17600	7747459	12.01
2	2016 -17	4576889	NA	1322884	922072	916828	3161784	29.17	7738673	1020	17102	7756795	11.89
3	2017 -18	4564054	NA	1310714	917045	932914	3160673	29.01	7724727	1014	21269	7747010	11.83
4	2018 -19	4440570	NA	1171319	828038	897901	2897258	28.58	7737828	668	20889	7759385	10.67
5	2019 -20	4520851	NA	1128328	767526	885437	2781291	27.60	7302142	32	00	7302174	10.51
6	2020 -21	4333327	279106	1098153	730958	905045	2734156	26.74	7346589	33	00	7346622	9.95
7	2021 -22	4094911	316857	1101221	720863	1192410	3014494	23.91	7426262	73	00	7426335	9.71
8	2022 -23	4130598	299390	1109120	709257	1221465	3039842	23.33	7469830	16	00	7469846	9.50
9	2023 -24	4037031	266905	1102613	686112	1209406	2998131	22.88	7302067	09	00	7302076	9.40
10	July, 2025	3822225	218878	1037973	630879	1160043	2828895	22.30	6869998	00	00	6869998	9.19
Avg		4314264	276227	1171921	784301	1016036	2972259	25.35	7464628	639.5	9451	7495302	10.46
SD		276071	37321	109694	108414	157372	154805	2.99	280611	609.9	10750	308829	1.18
CV		0.0640	0.135	0.0936	0.1382	15.49	5.21	11.18	3.76	95.37	113.7	4.12	11.28

										4		
CAGR	-0.0209	-5.90	-0.0277	-0.0422	3.67	-1.03	-3.22	-1.30	NA	NA	-1.33	-2.93
Maximum	4622104	316857	1336880	930262	1221465	3161784	29.94	7738673	1700	21269	7759385	12.01
Minimum	3822225	218878	1037973	630879	838913	2734156	22.30	6869998	00	00	6869998	9.19

Major Findings from Table-2

1. The average population associated with APL ration cards during the period April 2015 to July 2025 (data for 2024–25 not included) was 4,314,264, and the member count has been declining at a CAGR of –0.0209% year-on-year.
2. The average population associated with the total NFSA ration card category during the period April 2015 to July 2025 (data for 2024–25 not included) was 2,972,259, and the member count has been declining at a CAGR of –1.03% year-on-year.
3. The average population associated with AAY ration cards during the period April 2015 to July 2025 (data for 2024–25 not included) was 784,301, with a coefficient of variation (CV) of 0.1382. This relatively low CV value indicates low variation in the AAY population data. The AAY member count has been declining at a CAGR of –0.0422% year-on-year. Within the NFSA categories (BPL, PHH, and AAY), the average share of the AAY population/member count was 25.35%. In contrast, the average share of the AAY population/member count relative to the total population recorded on all ration cards for the period shown in the table was 10.46%.

Table-3. Year-wise Average family Member count of APL, NFSA & AAY

S	Year	1.Total APL cards (Beyond NFSA)	2. Total APL Mem (Beyond NFSA)	3Avg Mem coun t per APL Family	4.Total AAY Cards	5. Total AAY Mem Count	6. Avg AAY Mem Cou nt	4.TOTAL Cards Under NFSA	5. Total mem in NFSA	6. Avg Mem per Fami ly in NFS A	7.Total of ALL Type of Cards	8. Total of all Mem under all Ration Cards	9. Avg Mem count per Famil y
1	2015	1129835	4622104	4.09	194874	930262	4.77	696570	3106055	4.46	1832133	7747459	4.23

	-16												
2	2016	1120410	4576889	4.08	194091	922072	4.75	708466	3161784	4.46	1833756	7756795	4.23
	-17												
3	2017	1126884	4564054	4.05	193499	917045	4.74	710373	3160673	4.45	1842682	7747010	4.20
	-18												
4	2018	1155178	4440570	3.84	185070	828038	4.47	686926	2897258	4.21	1847035	7759385	4.20
	-19												
5	2019	1208968	4520851	3.74	178522	767526	4.30	677646	2781291	4.10	1886643	7302174	3.87
	-20												
6	2020	1242573	4612433	3.71	171202	730958	4.27	670801	2734156	4.07	1913408	7346622	3.84
	-21												
7	2021	1205091	4411768	3.66	169733	720863	4.25	742964	3014494	4.06	1948088	7426335	3.81
	-22												
8	2022	1220515	4429988	3.63	168179	709257	4.22	754261	3039842	4.03	1974790	7469846	3.78
	-23												
9	2023	1204515	4303936	3.57	165690	686112	4.14	754030	2998131	3.98	1958491	7302076	3.73
	-24												
10	July, 2025	1198381	4041103	3.37	161518	630879	3.91	745623	2828895	3.80	1944004	6869998	3.53
	Average	1181240	4452374	3.77	178238	784301	4.38	714766	2972258	4.16	1898103	7472770	3.94
	SD	44038	176560	0.24	12770	108414	0.29	32188.27	154805.2	0.23	56441.31	289277.2	0.25
	CV	3.73	3.97	6.36	7.16	0.14	0.07	4.5	0.0521	0.055	0.03	0.039	0.06
	CAGR	0.66	-1.48	-2.13	-2.06	-0.0422	-0.022	1.00	-0.0103	-0.018	0.007	-0.0133	-0.02
	Maximum	1242573	4622104	4.09	194874	930262	754261	754261	3161784	4.46	1974790	7759385	4.23
	Minimum	1120410	4041103	3.37	161518	630879	670801	670801	2734156	3.80	1832133	6869998	3.53

Major Findings from Table-3

1. From 2015–16 to July 2025, there has been an overall decline in the total number of beneficiaries in Himachal Pradesh. In 2015–16, the total number of members associated with all types of ration cards was 7,747,459, which declined to 6,869,998 by July 2025.

2. Over the last 10 years (April 2015 to July 2025; data for 2024–25 not included), the average member count per APL family was 3.77. The total APL member count declined at a CAGR of -1.48% , and the average family size declined at a CAGR of -2.13% , while the number of APL ration cards increased at a CAGR of 0.66% per year.
3. Over the last 10 years (April 2015 to July 2025; data for 2024–25 not included), the average member count per family covered under NFSA was 4.16. The total NFSA member count declined at a CAGR of -0.0103% , and the average family size declined at a CAGR of -0.018% , while NFSA ration cards increased at a CAGR of 1% per year.
4. Over the last 10 years (April 2015 to July 2025; data for 2024–25 not included), the average member count per AAY family was 4.38. The total AAY member count declined at a CAGR of -0.0422% , and the average family size declined at a CAGR of -0.022% , while AAY ration cards decreased at a CAGR of -2.06% per year.
5. Over the last 10 years (April 2015 to July 2025; data for 2024–25 not included), the average member count per family across all categories was 3.94. The total member count declined at a CAGR of -0.0133% , and the average family size declined at a CAGR of 0.02% , while the total number of ration cards increased marginally at a CAGR of 0.007% per year.

Conclusion:

The analysis reveals that while Upadhyay's 'Antyodaya' envisions holistic upliftment (economic, social, educational, and spiritual), the 'Antyodaya Anna Yojana' is a significant government effort to realize this comprehensive philosophy primarily through food security. This scheme exemplifies Upadhyay's call to 'no one should remain hungry' by directly benefiting the most disadvantaged sections of society. However, this research indicates that achieving the full goal of 'Antyodaya' requires focusing beyond subsidized food grains, but also on other aspects of self-reliance and quality of life. Also from above three tables we can conclude that:

From table-1 we can conclude that,

1. The distribution of AAY Ration cards for poorest of the poor families by the government of Bharat shows that the government of Bharat is serious for upliftment of Antyodaya families and for 'Zero Hunger' goal of SDG.

2. The number of ration cards under AAY are decreasing per year which reveals that the AAY families are coming out of that category of 'poorest of the poor' and becoming self-dependent in the field of their food necessities and the very poor families may be uplifted to some poor families.

3. Also, decrease in the number of BPL ration cards year on year basis reflects that the economic status of families improving.

From table-2 it is clear from the data that,

1. There is a decrease in total number of persons associated on APL and NFSA type of ration cards.
2. It is found that member count in NFSA Category and in AAY is decreasing regularly year on year basis. From which we can conclude the families are coming out from that very poor condition of AAY.
3. Also, data shows that the role of government on population control is working properly and government's family planning schemes working efficiently.

From table-3 it can concluded that,

1. The average family size of all the APL families for last 10 years from Apr,2015 to Jul,2025 (Data of 2024-25 not included) is least, that is 3.77 in all category of ration cards.
2. The family size of overall categories in NFSA is 4.16 and of AAY families have average size 4.38, which is more than the averages of the population attached with all other type of cards. Here, the family size is more than 4 has more expenses and more requirement of food grains for daily need. Hence more foodgrains should be provided to the AAY families.
3. There is a decrease in family member count of BPL families.
4. Above data also reveals that people in Himachal Pradesh are well aware of government-oriented family planning programs or the family planning and health department is doing well in this regard.
5. Average population associated with ration cards is decreasing and the number of ration cards increasing, also shows that our society is preferring nuclear families instead of joint families. Which is an alarming situation for our society.

Overall, we can conclude that the AAY beneficiary families have more number of average people associated with each Ration card as compare to APL cards. Hence the family size of AAY beneficiary families is more as compare to APL families. Hence they need more money and foodgrains for their basic

needs. Hence more foodgrains should be given to these families as per the size of the family. More the members in the family, more will be the foodgrains and other items will be provided to the AAY families on subsidized rates. From the data we can also say that so many families has come out of the very poor category of AAY. From the above analysis, it can also be concluded that the Antyodaya philosophy and the implementation of Antyodaya schemes have helped many families across the country to move out of conditions of extreme poverty.

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